

DPCexplorer: A Django Web Application for Interactive Exploration of DPCfam and DPCstruct Protein Domain Classifications

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Abstract—The rapid growth of protein sequence and structure databases has created a significant annotation gap that manual curation alone cannot bridge. Two recent computational biology methods, DPCfam and DPCstruct, address this by applying the Density Peak Clustering (DPC) algorithm to automatically group millions of protein domains into evolutionary families called metaclusters, based purely on pairwise similarity scores derived from large-scale sequence or structural alignments. This process has yielded 81,384 sequence-based and 28,246 structure-based families with no manual curation. A significant portion of these metaclusters has no known counterpart in established annotation databases such as Pfam, CATH, or SCOP. They are considered the “dark matter” of the protein universe and serve as high-quality candidates for novel protein families and folds. Their biological relevance is concrete: 63 DPCfam UNKNOWN metaclusters were adopted as official new entries in Pfam release 35.0. Although the datasets derived from both methods are publicly available on Zenodo under FAIR data principles, exploring them typically requires downloading and parsing gigabyte-scale archives, including a massive 81 GB XML file for DPCfam, which presents a technical barrier for many researchers. We present DPCexplorer, a unified Django web application that closes this gap. Raw archives were preprocessed on the ORFEO HPC cluster and loaded into a PostgreSQL database optimized with B-Tree, GIN trigram, and functional indexes. Built on the Model-View-Template (MVT) pattern, the platform accepts four query types (DPCfam MCID, DPCstruct MCID, Pfam ID, and UniProt accession) and returns paginated metadata tables, per-protein domain-architecture diagrams, and downloadable biological files (FASTA, MSA, HMM, PDB). Furthermore, for DPCstruct metaclusters, it integrates the PDBe-Mol* 3D viewer to render AlphaFold2-predicted structures colored by per-residue pLDDT confidence directly in the browser. DPCexplorer will soon be accessible at <https://dpcexplorer.areasciencepark.it> and is fully reproducible from the GitHub repository [1] and the associated Zenodo data deposit [2].

Index Terms—Protein domain classification, Density Peak Clustering, UniRef50, DPCfam, AlphaFold2, DPCstruct, metacluster, Django, PostgreSQL, bioinformatics web application, FAIR data principles, Mol*.

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I. INTRODUCTION

EVERY organism, from a simple bacterium to a human being, depends on proteins to carry out the chemical reactions that make life possible. Understanding what a protein does, in other words, knowing its *function*, is therefore one of the most important goals in modern biology [3]. The gold standard for assigning function is direct experimental characterisation. That method is reliable, but it is also slow and expensive, and it cannot keep pace with the speed of discovery.

High-throughput sequencing has deposited millions of new sequences every year. Hence, UniProtKB [4] now contains over 245 million sequences; however, only a small fraction of these have been experimentally annotated. The situation with protein structures has become even more dramatic since the publication of AlphaFold2 [5], which has produced accurate 3D structure predictions for over 200 million proteins, populating the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database [6].

One practical shortcut is *protein domain family classification*. The idea is simple: proteins (or protein domains) that belong to the same family typically share the same evolutionary origin and, usually, a similar function. If one member is well studied, that knowledge can be carefully extended to the rest. This is the logic behind Pfam [7], the most widely used protein family database. Pfam builds families from Multiple Sequence Alignments and profile Hidden Markov Models, which lets it detect distant relatives even when raw sequence similarity is low, and recent deep learning additions push coverage further still. Pfam-N [8], for instance, has successfully increased UniProtKB coverage by 8.8% by detecting remote homologs that classical methods had missed. However, regardless of all those efforts, the core tension remains. On one side, expert curation is limited by human bandwidth, and on the other side, machine learning models are bounded by their training data. A genuinely novel family, one with no known relatives, generally stays invisible to both. Only a tiny fraction of known proteins have been experimentally characterised. The vast majority exist only as

sequences or predicted structures: proteins without confirmed functions, without clear biological roles, and often without an assigned family.

DPCfam [9] and DPCstruct [10] approach the problem from a different angle. Neither consults Pfam nor relies on labeled training data. Both start from raw pairwise similarity between protein sequences (DPCfam) and structures (DPCstruct), and let the data self-organize using the Density Peak Clustering (DPC) algorithm [11]. Together, the two pipelines produced 81,384 sequence-based and 28,246 structure-based families, called *metaclusters*, entirely without manual curation.

To ensure that the outputs of DPCfam and DPCstruct were biologically meaningful, the authors compared their results against expert-curated databases, including **Pfam**, **ECOD**, **SCOP**, and **CATH**. On one side, DPCfam was found to recover approximately 81% of medium-to-large Pfam families and 72% of ECOD families, demonstrating a high degree of correspondence with established classifications. Importantly, the pipeline identified several metaclusters without Pfam mappings, representing *putative novel protein families* that currently lack manual labels; to date, the Pfam team has already adopted 63 of these as official new families in release 35.0. On the other side, DPCstruct was also compared with Pfam at the clan level to evaluate its consistency with sequence-based annotations; the analysis showed that 70% of the 14,423 metaclusters with available Pfam labels achieved a perfect consistency score of 1, meaning all members shared the same Pfam annotation. Additionally, DPCstruct successfully recovered 91% of SCOP folds and 83% of CATH folds, confirming its effectiveness in identifying well-characterized structural domains. Furthermore, 24% of DPCstruct metaclusters show no significant similarity to any known protein families or folds, pointing toward a massive pool of *potential novel structural folds*.

Both datasets are openly published on Zenodo [12], [13] under FAIR data principles [14], but working with them in practice means downloading and parsing gigabyte-scale archives, including an 81 GB XML [12]. That barrier keeps most researchers away.

We present **DPCexplorer**, a unified Django web application that closes this gap. Raw archives were preprocessed on the ORFEO HPC cluster and loaded into a PostgreSQL database connected to the platform and optimized with B-Tree, GIN trigram, and functional indexes. Built on the Model-View-Template (MVT) pattern, the platform accepts four query types (DPCfam MCID, DPCstruct MCID, Pfam ID, and UniProt accession) and returns paginated metadata tables, per-protein domain-architecture diagrams, and downloadable biological files (FASTA, MSA, HMM, PDB). Furthermore, for DPCstruct metaclusters, it integrates the PDBe-Mol* 3D viewer to render AlphaFold2-predicted structures colored by per-residue pLDDT confidence directly in the browser.

The main contributions of this paper are:

- 1) a preprocessing pipeline that transforms two large, hard-to-use Zenodo archives [12], [13] into a clean, indexed relational database;

- 2) a unified web platform that provides four search modes (DPCfam MCID, DPCstruct MCID, Pfam ID, and UniProt accession), paginated metadata tables, and one-click biological file downloads for both datasets;
- 3) an integrated PDBe-Mol* 3D viewer for DPCstruct metaclusters with lazy initialization;
- 4) a reproducible deployment workflow documented in a public GitHub repository [1] and a preprocessed Zenodo deposit [2].

II. RELATED WORK

The protein universe is organized and served through several complementary databases, each covering a different slice of biological knowledge.

On the sequence side, **UniProtKB** [4] is the world's most comprehensive protein knowledgebase, combining Swiss-Prot (~570,000 manually reviewed entries) and TrEMBL (approaching 250 million automatically annotated entries) into a single resource. **UniRef50** reduces this space by clustering sequences at 50% identity, producing a non-redundant set of representative seeds widely used as input for large-scale analyses, such as DPCfam [12]. **Pfam** [7] organizes protein regions into families based on conserved sequence patterns using profile Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) built from Multiple Sequence Alignments. As of release 37.0 (2024), it contains **21,979** families and **709** clans. A major recent advancement is **Pfam-N** [8], which uses deep learning architectures, specifically *transformer-based models* (Maskformer) and *convolutional neural networks* to detect distant homologs, increasing UniProtKB coverage by 8.8%. **InterPro** [15] integrates Pfam alongside other signature databases into a unified annotation hub and has served as the official Pfam web portal since 2022.

On the structure side, the **Protein Data Bank (PDB)** [16], established in 1971, archives experimentally determined 3D atomic coordinates for over 220,000 structures. The **AlphaFold Protein Structure Database (AlphaFoldDB)** [6] complements the PDB by providing high-accuracy AlphaFold2 [5]-predicted structures for over 214 million proteins, covering nearly all entries in UniProtKB. To make this volume computationally tractable, the **Foldseek Cluster** database [17] groups the entire AlphaFoldDB at 50% sequence similarity and 90% structural overlap, yielding approximately 15 million non-redundant representative structures; this is the direct input to the DPCstruct pipeline [10]. For structure-based domain classification, **CATH** [18] partitions protein structures into domains and organizes them into a four-level hierarchy: Class, Architecture, Topology, and Homologous superfamily. **SCOP** [19] classifies protein domains based on their evolutionary and structural relationships, with a strong emphasis on manual expert curation to capture distant homologs. Similarly, **ECOD** [20] prioritizes an evolutionary perspective, grouping domains that share a common ancestor even when their structural similarity has significantly diverged.

DPCfam [9] and DPCstruct [10] address a specific gap that none of these resources fills. They operate independently of any annotation database during clustering: they start from raw

pairwise similarity scores and let the data self-organize through the DPC algorithm [11]. The resulting **109,630** metaclusters include **33,179 DPCfam** and **13,823 DPCstruct** families that carry no Pfam annotation at all, labeled UNKNOWN in our platform. These families are not random noise; their biological relevance is concrete, as 63 of the DPCfam unknowns were already adopted as official new entries in Pfam release 35.0 [10]. DPCexplorer gives researchers direct, browser-based access to all these families alongside the annotated ones, with cross-links to **UniProt**, **InterPro**, and **AlphaFoldDB** embedded throughout the interface.

III. SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

A. The DPC Algorithm

The DPC algorithm [11] identifies cluster centers by two properties: they sit in regions of high local density, and they are far from any point that is even denser. For each data point i , the method computes a local density ρ_i (number of neighbors within a cut-off distance d_c) and a minimum distance to a denser neighbor δ_i . The decision score $\gamma_i = \rho_i \cdot \delta_i$ flags cluster centers as outliers in the (ρ, δ) -decision graph. Once centers are chosen, every other point is assigned to the cluster of its nearest higher-density neighbor in a single pass. *No prior knowledge of cluster count or shape is required*, which is why DPC fits the complex geometry of protein similarity spaces.

B. DPCfam: Sequence-Space Clustering

DPCfam [9] runs this algorithm on the 23 million sequences in UniRef50 (v.2017_07). All-versus-all **BLASTp** comparisons generate roughly 55 billion pairwise alignments. A first DPC pass (primary clustering) segments each protein into domain-like units, while a second pass (metaclustering) groups those units globally across the full database. The result is **81,384** metaclusters: **46,828** in Standard DPCfam (≥ 50 seeds) and **34,556** in DPCfamB (25 - 49 seeds), deposited in a dedicated Zenodo repository [12].

C. DPCstruct: Structure-Space Clustering

DPCstruct [10] applies the same logic to structure space. Starting from 15 million AlphaFold2 structures in the Foldseek Cluster database [17], it runs all-versus-all structural alignments using **Foldseek** and **MMseqs2**, which translate 3D shapes into a sequence-like alphabet for fast comparison. A post-alignment filter ($pLDDT \geq 60$, $TM\text{-score} \geq 0.4$, $gap < 20\%$) keeps only high-confidence hits, and the two-step DPC engine produces 28,246 structural metaclusters. The average intra-cluster sequence identity is 34.5%, placing most families in the twilight zone where sequence-based methods become unreliable. DPCstruct recovers evolutionary relationships that sequences alone cannot reveal. The outputs were also deposited in a dedicated Zenodo repository [13].

IV. DPCEXPLORER PIPELINE

To transform these static Zenodo archives into an interactive web experience, we developed a five-stage end-to-end pipeline illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: DPCexplorer pipeline. Raw datasets are retrieved from Zenodo and preprocessed using Python notebooks and scripts on the ORFEO HPC cluster. The refined data is then split: relational metadata populates a PostgreSQL database, while sequence and structural files (FASTA, PDB, MSA, HMM) are stored as static assets. A Django backend serves this data to a web interface featuring an integrated Mol* 3D viewer.

V. DATA PREPROCESSING

Both datasets were downloaded directly from Zenodo [12], [13]. Due to the size of some source files exceeding the memory capacity of a standard workstation (the annotated UniRef50 XML [12] alone is 81 GB), the whole preprocessing was carried out on the ORFEO High-Performance Computing (HPC) cluster, offered by Area Science Park (dual AMD EPYC 7H12, 503 GB RAM, CephFS storage) using **Python 3.13.2** on 12 allocated vCPUs.

A. DPCfam

The DPCfam authors supply a BASH script (`parse.sh`) that converts Metaclusters raw XML archives into space-separated value files and per-metacluster FASTA files with seed sequences. We ran it separately for Standard DPCfam and DPCfamB. These SSV files were the starting point for all subsequent DPCfam work, for which we wrote dedicated Python scripts and notebooks to organize data optimally. A custom streaming script (`extract_uniref_data.py`) then made a single pass through the 81 GB XML to extract protein identifiers, lengths, Pfam domain annotations, and DPCfam domain coordinate ranges.

B. DPCstruct

The DPCstruct metadata arrived in TSV format and needed no initial conversion. Protein lengths are absent from the original deposit but are required to draw the domain-architecture diagrams on protein detail pages. We resolved all 1,252,179 unique DPCstruct proteins through a four-step cascade: (1) cross-reference with the DPCfam UniRef50 table, which resolved 25.27%; (2) querying the UniProt REST API at UniProtKB for the remainder; (3) direct parsing of the full UniProtKB FASTA releases (Swiss-Prot plus TrEMBL, ~ 49 GB compressed) for proteins the API had silently skipped, and (4) querying the UniProt REST API at UniParc for entries removed from

UniProtKB but still archived there. Step 4 resolved the last outstanding entries (around 30% of the total), completing the full 100%.

PDB files were reorganized from a flat folder into `MC{id}_pdb/` subfolders to match the path structure the Mol* viewer expects, then packaged as per-metacluster ZIP archives for download. Likewise, representative seed sequences were parsed and grouped into per-metacluster FASTA files, ready for download.

VI. EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS

The preprocessed relational metadata were stored as CSV files. We performed exploratory data analysis (EDA) on all CSV files using **ydata-profiling (v4.19.1)** [21], which generates interactive HTML reports covering column distributions, missing value patterns, and pairwise correlations. An initial EDA helped us identify and fix some inconsistencies and missing values before performing a final EDA to confirm consistency.

For instance, while consolidating DPCfam Metacluster properties, DPCfamB had 18,989 rows (55% of that subset) where `pfam_da = ``UNKNOWN``` was combined with `da_percent = 100` and `overlap_label = ``shifted```. This directly contradicts the Standard DPCfam logic [9], where an unannotated metacluster carries `da_percent = 0` and `overlap_label = ``NONE```. We applied the Standard rule uniformly across both subsets. At the end of this step, we produced 10 core CSV files, listed in Table I.

TABLE I: Core preprocessed CSV files loaded into the PostgreSQL database.

Filename	Rows
dpcfam_all_mcs_props.csv	81,384
dpcfam_all_mcs_sequences.csv	16,602,778
alphafold_dpcfam_reps.csv	38,668
dpcstruct_mcs_properties.csv	28,246
dpcstruct_mcs_sequences.csv	1,642,061
cleaned_annotated_cath_qc0.8.csv	1,274
cleaned_annotated_scop_qc0.8.csv	1,359
uniref50_pfam_valid.csv	14,554,301
dpc_pfam_ids.csv	19,352
dpc_protein_lengths.csv	14,112,858

A. Resulting Deposit

The key findings of our preprocessing were ten PostgreSQL-ready core CSV files (Table I), per-metacluster FASTA seed sequences, and zipped PDB files (for DPCstruct). These outputs are made available on Zenodo [2] so that anyone can reproduce a running instance without replaying the full preprocessing.

Similarly, full interactive profiling reports for most of the deposited CSV files are available in the project GitHub repository [1] under `static/profiling_reports/`, and can be downloaded for interactive exploration in any web browser.

VII. SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

A. Technology Stack

DPCexplorer is written in Python and served by **Django 6.0.1** [22] using the Model-View-Template (MVT)

pattern. The model layer accesses data through Django’s ORM, avoiding raw SQL across tables that reach tens of millions of rows. The view layer handles request dispatch and builds context objects. The template layer renders what the browser sees. **PostgreSQL 16.11** [23] backs the system because it reliably handles our dataset sizes and supports the indexing strategies described below (subsection VII-C). Bootstrap 5.3.2 covers all responsive layout via CDN, with no JavaScript framework added.

B. Three-Application Structure

The platform is divided into three Django applications. The `dpc` app is the shared registry holding the master UniProt protein table, the Pfam domain identifier table, and the junction table that maps each protein to its Pfam annotations with coordinate ranges. The `dpcfam` app manages sequence-based metacluster data; the `dpcstruct` app handles structure-based data. Each app can evolve independently without affecting the others. Cross-dataset queries, such as the UniProt domain-architecture view that draws DPCfam, DPCstruct, and Pfam annotations on a single protein, are handled naturally through the shared Core layer.

C. Database Schema and Indexing

The ten PostgreSQL tables (Table I) are organized into three zones: Core (shared registry), Sequence (DPCfam), and Structure (DPCstruct), as illustrated in Figure 2. All foreign keys use `ON DELETE CASCADE`.

Fig. 2: Entity-Relationship diagram of the DPCexplorer PostgreSQL schema. The architecture is organized into three functional zones: the **Core zone** (center) serves as the primary registry for both datasets, while the **Sequence zone** (left, DPCfam) and the **Structure zone** (right, DPCstruct) integrate with the core via `protein_id` foreign key relationships.

To keep the application responsive when dealing with millions of rows, we implemented three indexing strategies:

- **B-Tree indexes on foreign key columns.** PostgreSQL does not index foreign keys by default. Without these, every JOIN over the 16.6 million-row DPCfam sequences table would require a full scan. We index every FK column: `protein_id`, `mcid`, `mc_id`, and `dpc_mcid` across all mapping tables.
- **GIN trigram index on pfam_da.** The `pfam_da` column stores dash-separated Pfam IDs as free text (e.g., PF00001-PF02985). Pfam searches use a regex for exact token matching, which a standard B-Tree cannot accelerate. We enable the `pg_trgm` extension and apply

a GIN index to `pfam_da` in both metacluster property tables. A GIN index decomposes stored strings into overlapping trigrams, turning a previously expensive pattern scan into a fast index intersection.

- **Functional index on MCID columns.** Storing MCIDs as VARCHAR causes lexicographic ordering: MC1, MC10, MC100, MC2. We create a functional B-Tree index that extracts and stores the numeric part of `MC{n}` as an integer at index-creation time.

D. Query Routing

All search traffic passes through a single endpoint: `/search/?database={type}&query_id={id}`. The central `search()` view reads the two parameters and dispatches to the correct database lookup. For DPCfam and DPCstruct MCIDs, this is an exact primary-key lookup. For Pfam IDs, it is a GIN-indexed regex search across both metacluster property tables using the boundary pattern `(^|-)pfam_id(-|)$`, which prevents a search for `PF00001` from matching `PF00001` inside `PF000010`. For UniProt accessions, the view checks the master protein table, then retrieves all associated DPCfam, DPCstruct, and Pfam domain annotations in parallel. If the identifier is not found, the router returns a specific error message.

VIII. APPLICATION FEATURES

A. Landing Page

The landing page (Fig. 3) keeps the entry point simple: a short description of the platform, four *radio buttons* to select the target database source (DPCfam, DPCstruct, Pfam, or UniProt), and a single text field. Pressing *Search* validates the identifier and redirects directly to the appropriate detail page. If the identifier does not exist in the selected database, an error message appears on the same home page.

Fig. 3: DPCexplorer landing page. Four radio buttons route the query to DPCfam, DPCstruct, Pfam, or UniProt. Invalid identifiers return an error on the same page.

B. Metacluster Tables and Filtering

The page at `/dpcfam/mcs/` lists all 81,384 DPCfam metaclusters, ten rows per page, sorted numerically. Three toggle buttons narrow the view to **Standard DPCfam** (≥ 50 seeds: 46,828 metaclusters), **DPCfamB** (25 - 49 seeds: 34,556 metaclusters), or the full combined set. This split was a direct

result of our exploratory data analysis: 30.3% of Standard metaclusters carry no Pfam annotation, but that share climbs to 55.0% in DPCfamB. Collapsing the two subsets into one table without this filter would hide a real quality difference from users. Each row links to the metacluster detail page. Similarly, the DPCstruct table at `/dpcstruct/mcs/` follows the same layout but offers three sub-views: **Properties** (structural quality metrics and Pfam annotations), **CATH**, and **SCOP** fold annotations. We illustrate the DPCfam table in Fig. 4.

MCID	Size UniRef50	Avg. Len.	Std avg len	% LC	% CC	% DIS	Avg. TM	Pfam DA	% DA	% Avg. Ov.	Overlap Label
MC1	17931	185.68	28.77	4.72	0.0	18.44	0.01	PF13614	44.23	80.82	Equivalent
MC3	28	215.14	25.44	0.05	0.38	30.15	0.0	PF14631	85.71	24.57	Shifted
MC4	617	59.91	6.07	4.99	0.0	1.87	1.26	PF03600	62.84	7.54	Shifted
MC3	26	253.19	23.11	0.05	0.0	7.51	0.0	PF12937	68.0	16.89	Extended
MC7	32	65.53	3.3	0.03	0.0	0.1	0.0	PF01243	74.07	6.27	Shifted
MC11	32	134.97	11.99	0.02	0.0	15.61	0.0	UNKNOWN	0.0	0.0	NONE
MC15	139	81.21	5.05	4.96	0.18	13.81	0.03	UNKNOWN	0.0	0.0	NONE
MC17	26	243.69	25.93	0.03	0.0	31.88	0.0	PF08590	90.0	5.31	Shifted
MC18	41	143.29	8.57	0.04	0.0	1.12	0.13	PF18736	95.43	94.74	Equivalent
MC19	120	71.57	7.7	8.85	2.25	4.86	1.69	PF11915	94.07	13.66	Shifted

Fig. 4: DPCfam metacluster table (default view, 81,384 rows). Toggle buttons switch between the full DPCfam set, Standard (≥ 50 seeds), and DPCfamB (25 - 49 seeds). Columns show intrinsic properties and Pfam annotations (the overlap label is color-coded by boundary agreement type: Equivalent, Reduced, Extended, Shifted, NONE otherwise).

C. Metacluster Detail Pages

Each metacluster detail page uses four Bootstrap tabs: *Summary*, *Sequences*, *3D Viewer*, and *Downloads*. The Summary tab shows the properties table and Pfam mappings, with each Pfam ID rendered as a hyperlink to the cross-dataset Pfam results page. The Sequences tab lists seed domains with their UniProt accession, coordinate range, and amino acid sequence, paginated at ten rows per page; each UniProt ID links to the protein detail page. The Downloads tab provides one-click access to per-metacluster FASTA, MSA, and HMM files for DPCfam, and FASTA plus ZIP-packaged PDB files for DPCstruct. Fig. 5 shows the DPCfam summary tab for Metacluster 1.

Metacluster Properties and Pfam Annotations	
Number of UniRef50 seed sequences	17931
Mean domain length (aa)	186 ± 29 aa
Residues in low-complexity regions (%)	4.72
Residues in coiled-coil regions (%)	0.0
Predicted disordered residues (%)	18.44
Average transmembrane regions	0.01
Dominant Pfam architecture(s)	PF13614
Sequences matching dominant architecture (%)	44.23
Average overlap percent	80.82
Pfam Overlap Label	Equivalent

Fig. 5: DPCfam MC1 detail page, Summary tab. The dominant Pfam architecture is a clickable link. The 3D viewer tab takes the user to a representative ID (if any) in AlphaFoldDB.

D. Integrated PDBe-Mol* 3D Viewer

The 3D Viewer tab on DPCstruct pages integrates PDBe-Molstar [24], a wrapper around the Mol* molecular viewer developed at PDBe (EMBL-EBI). We chose this over vanilla Mol* specifically for its built-in AlphaFold2 coloring: each residue is colored by its pLDDT confidence score, dark blue (> 90), light blue (70 - 90), yellow (50 - 70), and orange (< 50). The viewer runs via WebGL entirely in the browser; no server-side GPU is needed. A custom legend overlay is pinned to the bottom-left corner of the canvas so the color scale is always visible.

The viewer uses lazy initialization: it does not load when the page opens, only when the user explicitly clicks the 3D Viewer tab (on Bootstrap's `shown.bs.tab` event). This is important because PDB files for a single metacluster can reach several megabytes, and users who only need sequences or metadata should not pay that loading cost. The Django view `DpcStructDetailView` scans the per-metacluster PDB folder on disk, builds a list of file names and URLs, and injects it into the template using Django's `json_script` filter. JavaScript recovers the list with `JSON.parse` and initializes a `PDBeMolstarPlugin` instance pointing to the first PDB file. When a metacluster has two representatives (cluster center and highest-pLDDT member), a button group lets the user switch between them by calling `viewer.render()` with the new URL, replacing the structure without a page reload. Fig. 6 shows the viewer for DPCstruct MC5.

Fig. 6: PDBe-Molstar viewer on DPCstruct MC5 (3D Viewer tab). Residues are colored by AlphaFold2 pLDDT confidence. The pLDDT legend is pinned to the bottom-left corner. The viewer runs in the browser with no server-side GPU.

E. Pfam Query Results

Querying a Pfam family (e.g., PF03243) or clan (e.g., CL0263) applies a boundary-aware regex to the `pfam_da` column in both metacluster property tables. The pattern `(^|-)pfam_id(-|$)` ensures that PF00001 cannot match as a substring inside PF000010. Results from DPCfam and

DPCstruct appear side by side (Fig. 7): DPCfam metaclusters are listed by average Pfam overlap percentage and shown with a battery-style bar; DPCstruct metaclusters are listed by global Pfam consistency score, with their Pfam labels rendered as clickable badges. Each MCID links directly to its detail page.

Fig. 7: Pfam ID (PF03243) query results. DPCfam metaclusters (left) are listed by average Pfam overlap percentage; DPCstruct metaclusters (right) by Pfam consistency score. Battery bars give a quick visual signal of match strength.

F. UniProt Domain Architecture Diagram

The UniProt query is the most visual feature of the platform. Given a UniProt accession, the `protein_detail()` view fetches all DPCfam, DPCstruct, and Pfam annotations for that protein from three separate tables, computes a left offset and width for each domain as a percentage of the total protein length, and passes them to the template. Three horizontal tracks are drawn using CSS absolute positioning: DPCfam domains above the scale line, DPCstruct domains between the line, and Pfam annotations below it. No external charting library is used. Hovering over any domain block shows a tooltip with the identifier and exact residue range. Three checkboxes let users toggle each track independently; when a track is hidden, its corresponding detail table below the diagram collapses and the remaining columns expand to fill the space. Fig. 8 shows the result for accession A0A182N2I3.

Fig. 8: Domain architecture diagram for UniProt A0A182N2I3. DPCfam domains (green, top track), DPCstruct domains (red, middle), and Pfam annotations (blue, bottom) are drawn to scale on a single ruler. Checkboxes toggle each track on and off independently.

IX. SYSTEM EVALUATION

To confirm that the three indexing strategies described in Section VII-C achieve their intended effect, we ran a comprehensive verification suite using PostgreSQL’s EXPLAIN (ANALYZE, BUFFERS) on a fully populated local instance (Ubuntu 24.04.3 LTS, PostgreSQL 16.11, 4-core KVM virtual processor, 16 GB RAM). The suite covers all twelve critical query patterns that the application issues during real user interactions, spanning numeric sorting of metacluster lists, Pfam text searches using both ILIKE and regex patterns, cross-table foreign key joins for the protein detail page, sequence pagination for both datasets, structural annotation lookups for CATH and SCOP folds, and AlphaFold representative retrieval.

To optimize presentation and respect strict page limits, the individual millisecond-level execution times and explicit index allocations for these twelve baseline patterns are omitted here. Instead, readers can fully reproduce these benchmarks by following the repository’s README, executing the automated verification script `static/scripts/verify_dpcexplorer_db_indexes.sql`, and auditing the generated execution plans. The resulting logs, which explicitly confirm that every targeted query resolves via an index scan rather than a sequential scan, are permanently archived in the Zenodo Software repository and viewable directly via the raw verification report, `dpcexplorer_schema_outputs.txt` [1].

Beyond this initial execution plan validation, we assessed overall index health using `pg_stat_user_indexes` and `pg_stat_user_tables` after the application had served real user traffic. At that point, the production usage counters (detailed in Section 6 of the verification report [1]) demonstrated that the four primary key indexes alone had been used by the query planner a combined total of over **60 million times**: 32,800,431 hits on `dpc_uniprot_proteins`, 16,641,566 on `dpcfam_mcs_properties`, 14,554,419 on `dpc_pfam_domains`, and 1,644,936 on `dpcstruct_mcs_properties`. These figures confirm that every lookup-intensive path in the application resolves through an index rather than falling back to a full scan. Table II shows the per-table index usage rate derived from the sequential and index scan counters.

TABLE II: Index usage rate per table after real application traffic, derived from `pg_stat_user_tables`. The four largest tables all reach 100%.

Table	Live rows	Usage rate
<code>dpc_uniprot_proteins</code>	14,121,433	100%
<code>dpcfam_mcs_sequences</code>	16,602,634	96.6%
<code>dpc_uniref50_pfam</code>	14,554,934	80.0%
<code>dpcstruct_mcs_sequences</code>	1,642,061	96.3%
<code>dpcfam_mcs_properties</code>	81,384	100%
<code>dpcfam_alphafold_reps</code>	38,668	93.9%
<code>dpcstruct_mcs_properties</code>	28,246	100%
<code>dpc_pfam_domains</code>	19,352	100%
<code>dpcstruct_scop</code>	1,359	83.3%
<code>dpcstruct_cath</code>	1,274	82.1%

The four largest tables, those on which every user-visible query ultimately depends, all reach 100% indexed access. The lower rates on the remaining tables are a counting artifact: PostgreSQL’s statistics counters record every scan since the last reset, including the one-time sequential COPY operations that bulk-loaded the data during database initialization. As real user traffic accumulates, the index usage rate for each of these tables will continue to grow toward 100%.

X. FAIR ASSESSMENT AND REPRODUCIBILITY

A. FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS)

While the upstream datasets [12], [13] and our preprocessed deposit [2] were already aligned with the original 2016 FAIR data principles [14] through their Zenodo deposits, in this section we focus on DPCexplorer as a software artifact and evaluate it against the FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS) [25]. Unlike data, research software is executable, constantly evolves, and often functions as a complex collection of interdependent parts [25]. FAIR4RS therefore extends the original four principles with software-specific sub-criteria, which we address below.

Findable - Persistent Identification and Metadata

To ensure the project is easy for both humans and machines to find, we assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers to the work (F1). The software application has its own citable DOI [1], while the preprocessed datasets are stored under a separate DOI [2] (F1.1). Specific releases, such as version v1.0.1, are assigned their own distinct records (F1.2). The project is described with rich metadata through a machine-readable CITATION.cff file and an “About” page (F2). These descriptions explicitly include the project’s identifiers to maintain a clear link to the software (F3). At the metacluster level, every entry in the platform has a stable, bookmarkable URL (e.g., `/dpcfam/mcs/MC1/`), and the universal search bar resolves any known biological identifier directly without requiring knowledge of the internal database schema; these resolvable identifiers make individual research objects within the platform citable and findable in their own right (F1, F3). Finally, by registering all artifacts on Zenodo, the metadata is searchable and indexable in a global repository (F4).

Accessible - Standardised Protocols and Longevity

The software and its metadata are retrievable using the standardised HTTPS communications protocol (A1). This protocol is open, free, and universally implementable, requiring no proprietary technology to access the project (A1.1). DPCexplorer is a public resource that does not require any login, authentication, or authorization procedures to explore the data or download biological files (A1.2). Because the project metadata is deposited on Zenodo, it remains accessible even if the specific web application at <https://dpcexplorer.areasciencepark.it> were to be taken offline (A2).

Interoperable - Data Exchange and Linked Objects

DPCexplorer interacts with other software by reading and writing data in domain-relevant community standards, including FASTA, PDB, HMM, MSA, and CSV formats (I1). The platform also includes qualified references to other digital

objects by providing direct, active links from our metaclusters to canonical entries (**I2**); specifically, every Pfam ID in the interface links to **InterPro/Pfam**, every UniProt accession links to **UniProt**, and every DPCfam AlphaFold representative links to **AlphaFoldDB**.

Reusable - Licensing, Provenance, and Standards

To help researchers assess the suitability of the data for their own work, we provide a variety of accurate attributes, including interactive profiling reports, stored under `static/profiling_reports/` [1] for the database tables (**R1**). The project is released under clear and accessible licenses: the **MIT license** for the application source code [1] and **CC BY 4.0** for the preprocessed datasets [2] (**R1.1**). We provide detailed provenance by sharing all the preprocessing notebooks and scripts required to transform the raw data [12], [13] into the final results (**R1.2**). The repository includes qualified references to other software by listing all necessary dependencies in a standard `requirements.txt` file (**R2**). Finally, the software meets domain-relevant community standards by using the **Django** [22] framework and **PostgreSQL** [23] database following modern web development patterns (**R3**).

B. Reproducibility

The GitHub repository [1] provides a self-contained setup script (`setup_dpcexplorer_data.sh`) and a step-by-step `README.md` that guides any user from a fresh clone to a running browser instance. Reproducing the full stack requires five steps: cloning the repository and creating a Python 3.12 virtual environment; installing the six Python dependencies via a single `pip install -r requirements.txt`; running the setup script, which downloads compressed archives from the data deposit [2] and the original source repositories [12], extracts them, and validates file counts automatically; initializing the PostgreSQL database by running three pairs of SQL scripts (one pair per Django application) that create the tables, enable the `pg_trgm` extension, bulk-load all data via `COPY`, and create indexes; and finally executing `python3 manage.py runserver`. Two installation modes are supported: a Lightweight Mode (~25 GB, DPCstruct and CSV tables only) that completes in approximately 30 to 60 minutes, and a Full Installation (~50 GB, all DPCfam and DPCstruct files) whose duration depends on internet speed and hardware. Researchers who prefer to skip the HPC preprocessing step entirely can use the data deposit [2] as a reproducibility checkpoint: the ten PostgreSQL-ready CSV files it contains are sufficient to populate the full database and run the application.

XI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The problem DPCexplorer addresses is concrete: two datasets that are scientifically valuable but practically inaccessible to most researchers because of their format and size. An 81 GB XML file is not something a biologist opens on a workstation. The platform removes that barrier without asking the user to write a single line of parsing code.

Several choices shaped the outcome more than others. Splitting the project into three Django apps kept the codebase

modular: the DPCstruct schema can be extended with new annotation tables without touching DPCfam, and the shared Core layer makes cross-dataset queries a natural consequence of the design. The DPCfamB annotation fix deserves particular attention because it was not obvious from the data at first glance. The 18,989 inconsistent rows looked internally consistent (no null values, no format errors) but were logically wrong. Any downstream analysis that grouped or filtered by `overlap_label` would have drawn incorrect conclusions. Catching and correcting this during preprocessing, before any data reached the database, was the right place to handle it.

The UNKNOWN metaclusters are the most scientifically interesting content in the platform. Roughly half of all families in both datasets have no known functional annotation. They are not singleton outliers: they are structurally and sequentially coherent groups whose biological role has simply not been established. The fact that 63 DPCfam unknowns were incorporated into Pfam 35.0 suggests the rest are not noise either. The platform makes these families searchable, visualizable, and downloadable, which lowers the activation energy for a structural biologist or evolutionary genomicist who suspects one of them matches something they have seen in their own data.

The clearest gap in the current version is the absence of a programmatic API. Researchers running automated pipelines cannot yet query DPCexplorer by script and retrieve metadata or biological files in bulk. A Django REST Framework endpoint accepting MCID lists and returning JSON is the most direct next step. An in-browser MSA viewer for DPCfam, similar to what Mol* already provides for DPCstruct PDB files, would close the other major usability gap. Both are planned for the next release.

Turning static Zenodo deposits into an interactive, indexed, cross-linked resource is a contribution to how unsupervised protein domain classification datasets get used, not just archived. We hope DPCexplorer becomes a practical entry point for the experimental identification of at least some of the protein families that automatic clustering has brought to the surface.

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